

Hepatitis & Nanomedicine: A Review

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ABSTRACT

In the year 1989, hepatitis C virus (HCV) was specifically established as causative factor accountable for many more occurrences of hepatitis. It's a chronic disease which majorly contributes to Carcinoma and Cirrhosis. The hepatitis C virus belongs a family Flaviviridae (+) enveloped ssRNA virus. It has been described that seven major genotypes of HCV and their subtypes (a, b). Around 3 percent among global residents has been infected by HCV. HCV Transmission is frequently associated with direct percutaneous blood contact, via blood transfusions, health-related injections and substance use injections. Several new therapies have been developed to treat HCV, such as polyethylene glycol (PEG)-ylated interferon / ribavirin, antivirals acting directly and antivirals targeting the host. Despite progress in anti-HCV therapy, there is still an urgent need for new approaches of targeted drug delivery systems using nanomedicine which are affordable and reliable. Nanotechnology has the ability to play a pivotal role in lowering viral load levels and drug-resistant HCV by targeting drugs directly to the disease site. In addition to tissue targeting, a wide variety of drugs need to be administered intracellularly to achieve a therapeutic effect in the organ affected. The contribution of nanoparticles as a promising delivery mechanism for HCV immunizing, diagnostic and therapeutic agents and there latest developments of drug carriers as well as their role in anti-HCV therapy were addressed in this review.

KEY WORDS: hepatitis c virus, flaviviridae, antivirals, interferon, nanotechnology

INTRODUCTION:

In the beginning of 21st century, two viruses (hepatitis A and hepatitis B), are major causative factors for hepatitis. While it was authenticated as early as 1950 for the third form of hepatitis, it wasn't till 1970, when blood examinations related to HAV, HBV became accessible, that the new agent referred to as non-A, non-B hepatitis (NANBH) has been recognized^[1]. It became clear after the launch of the HBV blood test; NANBH is accountable for hepatitis^[2]. Sufficient research work has been carried out with respect to isolation of this virus along with its therapy also. HCV came to be recognized as main factor for NANBH, was recognized as silent pandemic. HCV was found in the year 1988. Laboratory tests have been valid for detecting HCV infections since 1989^[3-4]. HCV is a major human pathogen borne in the blood. Approximately 3% global residents has been HCL

infected. As per WHO data, about 30 to 40 lakh new infections has been annually reported^[5-6]. HCV has been identified as a main health related trouble, which can further leads to Cirrhosis, Carcinoma. In advanced all region, intravenous substance misuse is the most effective route for HCV transmission, while in developing region injection therapy causes new infections^[7]. Major infections lead to chronic conditions without treatment, accompanied with cirrhosis and HCC. Misuse of alcohol and dysmetabolic syndrome are the primary co-factor affecting advanced liver disease and HCC development^[8]. Approximately 30 percentages of liver transplants are performed annually in persons with HCV-related problems, with decompensated cirrhosis or HCC^[9]. The concern of hepatitis C is projected to increase in the next decade because of the aging of the currently infected population^[10-11]. During this time, the number of HCV-related cases of cirrhosis is expected to increase by 31% and HCC by around 50%^[10] with an additive effect due to the incidence of the metabolic syndrome^[12-13]. HCV infection is therefore a significant public health problem that should be resolved through strong policy measures aimed at efficiently detecting and treating patients infected with HCV. Seven genotypes (gt 1-7), and several HCV subtypes are

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there. The rate of infection and the prevalence of the subtype are dependent on the region. In less and more endemic countries, the gap between the infection rate is around 20 percent^[14-15]. For example, the HCV prevalence is the lowest in North America, Western North Europe and Australia. In comparison, the prevalence of the virus is high in Asian and African countries. Egypt has reported the highest prevalence of viruses, where 22 percent of the population is infected^[16]. It was postulated that during the period of parenteral-anti-schistosomal mass treatment campaigns prior to 1985, the outbreak was triggered by widespread iatrogenic transmission^[17].

Virology:

HCV is a RNA virus with a positive-sense, single-stranded 9600 kb weight. A single HCV polyprotein of 3011 amino acids is translated in three structural proteins and seven non-structural proteins by the cellular and viral proteases^[18]. Linked viral sequences in dogs^[19], horses^[20], rats, and bats^[21] were identified. HCV infection in human populations display significant genetic variation, clarified in part by the long evolutionary relationship between the virus and humans^[22]. Many studies have focused on first six genotypes HCV. All the genotypes are globally distributed, in African region 1, 2, 4 and 5 genotypes; in Asian region 3 and 6 genotypes has been distributed^[23]. Medical initiatives related to schistosomiasis have been escalated in Egypt over the last century^[24]. In United Kindom, genotype 3a is a coinfluenced trait of 1a genotype which has indications for vaccine therapy. In addition, HCV have immense genetical diverseness in contaminated carriers, which occurs as a swarm of associated quasi species in the blood. This diversity is the product of error-prone viral polymerase, and rapid viral multiplication allows rapid accommodation to the antibody response, cellular immune response and antiviral drugs^[25]. HCV growth in tissue culture was not possible until a particular strain of the HCV genotype 2 was discovered^[26]. HCV culture was used to classify a diverse collection of surface receptor interactions, including CD81, SCARB1 (a scavenger receptor) and two close junction proteins, OCLN and CLDN1^[27].

These models allowed the creation of critical insights into viral multiplication and host – virus interactions^[28]. Study using Electron microscopy reflected that mature viruses are having atypical structural arrangements^[29].

Significantly, capability to study tissue culture HCV multiplication associated with structure related protein analysis which has led to the optimization of new unique DAAs^[30-32].

Immunology:

Cell mediated immunological reactions to HCV influences consequences of acute illness along with the progression of lengthy illnesses. Acute immunological reactions to HCV include both innate branches of the immune system and adaptive ones. Polymorphic changes in IL28B gene have a strong influence on spontaneous infection resolution^[33]. IFNL3 codes of interferon, lambda 3, which is having antiviral response same as response of interferon, but with limited receptor distribution. It remains to be clarified whether polymorphisms recognized affect the control of IFNL3 or IFNL4^[34]. Similarly, linkages between genes in the KIR (Killer cell immunoglobulin-like receptors) locus along with infection resolution reflects natural (killer) cell reactions plays an important role in virus associated regulation^[35]. Acute host defense involves adaptive responses regulated with the help of CD8 cells and CD4 T cells. Many studies have reported more combinations via HLA class II alleles, along with good-powered genome-wide association case study^[33]. Association of HLA class-I was recognized at single source epidemic^[36]. CD4 cell mediated reaction and CD8 T-cell mediated reactions are necessary in complete safety of chimpanzees^[37]. As a consequence of these kind of studies, there is a need to optimize T cell-based protective vaccines that is based on 2 recombinant vectors^[38]. Also studied in detail were B cell responses to HCV, which lead to the generation of neutralizing antibodies^[39]. The variability of regions such as the HCV E2 envelope protein hyper variable regions within hosts is a result of immune selection driven by anticorps. However, broadly cross-reactive neutralizing antibodies have been described^[40] and further work to characterize these antibodies could lead to the development of antibody-based vaccines, particularly in the context of the recently described HCV E2 crystal structure^[41].

Epidemiology:

HCV is most efficiently transmitted through percutaneous blood exposure/transfusion, organ transplantation (which may be infected previously) and injection use for medication purpose^[42]. Exposure of mucosa with any blood or serum that makes transmission far less effective^[43-44]. Transfusion via blood was a main cause behind HCV infection prior to testing and that transfusion mode was eliminated in regions where blood donor's screening generally conducted^[45]. Drug use injection is the biggest risk factor in the United States and Australia, and accounts for most new diagnoses of HCV infection in Europe^[42]. In addition to the sharing of needles, the sharing of other

things such as foil and spoons was involved in the transmission of HCV^[46]. Transmission of sexual and perinatal HCV does occur but to a significantly lesser extent than with hepatitis B. Perinatal transmission in mothers co-infected with HIV occurs at a rate of about 4% and is two to four times higher^[47]. As of today no proof present from randomly regulated testing for showing superiority of caesarean section against normal (vaginal) mode of delivery in maternity^[48].

Ratio of transmission via sexual intercourse remains debatable; in normal hetero sexual associations rate is very minimal. Co-infection with HIV, relationship duration, or chronic liver disease may be independent cofactors that increase the risk of transmission^[49]. Further sexual risk factors for transmission were indicated by data from a UK case-control study of acute HCV infection in men who have sex with men attending HIV clinics in three urban centres. Infection had been associated with percutaneous rather than percutaneous transmission factors. Compared with controls, men with acute HCV had more sexual partners, showed increased sexual behaviour at high risk, and were more likely to have shared drugs in the previous year via a nasal or anal route. Sex was the strongest predictor of case or control status in a group of more than two people^[50]. HCV along with HIV co-transfusion is a major health risk, with about 10% persons who are having HIV infection at the same time are also having infection of HCV globally^[51]. In many advanced regions risk is from 25% to 50-95% in many risk sectors (though many HCV infected persons are not HIV infected)^[52]. HIV infection is having major effect on the viral load of HCV infection^[53] also on the clinically progression of a disease^[54].

Chronic hepatitis C and its pathophysiology:

This disease also not result of direct damage of liver cells via infection of HCV. Chronic hepatitis C generally results through intermediate immunological reaction which is large to enhance hepatocellular damage. This kind of immunological reaction is not sufficient to expell virus and culminates in fibrosis along with liver cirrhosis. In quantitative terms, in the chronic phase, HCV-specific CD4 reaction along with CD8 T-cell mediated reaction is weak as compared to acute phase of viral infection. Patients with poor acute response are often asymptomatic (no jaundice) and are more likely than those with high immune responses to become chronic carriers^[55].

HCV specific CD8 cells have an impaired effector function (both the secretion of antiviral cytokines and lytic activity).

Clinical illustration:

Acute HCV disease is scientifically identical from many responses of acute viral hepatitis infection. That can cause high fever, muscular pain along with discomfort feeling sensations. Usually the acute phase is asymptomatic though. Following acute HCV infection, subsequent events vary significantly between patients but three patterns were noted:

- Ø Viral clearance (below blood detection level)
- Ø Viral durability without host regulation
- Ø Midway phase (virus is momentarily regulated along with recurrence)

Almost 80% HCV-infected persons leads to the chronic phase of viral infection which generally exists for minimum 180 days post viral onset. Infection rates vary by age, gender, ethnicity, HCV genotype and immune system status^[56]. For example, HIV-infected patients are rapidly progressing to liver disease, whereas in West Africa, where genotype 2 infection predominates, the clearance rate is 50% due to the high frequency HLA-B*57 in that population^[57]. A cohort of Irish women infected with contaminated blood products (genotype 1b) had similar protection levels and data showed that specific class II HLA alleles were associated with HCV clearance^[58]. Findings of other studies in different populations have shown associations with HLA DQB1*0301 and DRB1*1101, and viral clearance^[59]. Although the natural history of HCV infection is believed to be very variable, up to about 20% of chronically infected individuals will develop cirrhosis of the liver over a 20-25-year period, and these people are at increased risk for development of end-stage liver disease and hepatocellular carcinoma [60]. Specific groups are associated with rapid progression of HCV-induced liver fibrosis, including men, people older than age 40 years at time of infection, and individuals who consume 50ml or more of alcohol a day^[61], in addition to patients co-infected with HIV [62]. Insulin resistance, obesity, and steatosis can accelerate fibrosis progression in chronic HCV^[63]. In fact, insulin resistance has been reported as a specific feature of chronic HCV infection (as compared to chronic hepatitis B) and is associated with genotypes 1 and 4^[64]. There is no understanding of the mechanism by which sex affects disease progression; however, an anti-fibrogenic role for oestrogens has been proposed. Menopause was recognized as an independent factor associated with a high stage of fibrosis in a prospective study of 251 women with chronic HCV, and hormone replacement had a protective role^[65]. Approximately 3-4 per cent of patients with cirrhosis develop hepatocellular carcinoma per year^[66]. Predictions are

that over the next 20-30 years the burden of HCV-associated cancer will rise substantially. This estimate is consistent with recent US data showing an increased prevalence of hepatocellular carcinoma in patients with HCV infection in younger age groups^[67]. Several extrahepatic manifestations of HCV infection have been reported, with up to 40-74 per cent of patients developing at least one of these disorders during their illness^[68]. In addition to hepatotropism, HCV exhibits particular lymphotropism and this effect could account for many extrahepatic manifestations^[69]. The most known and studied syndrome in HCV infection is mixed cryoglobulinemia. Cryoglobulins are immunoglobulins that precipitate below 37 ° C, resulting in systemic vasculitis characterised by the deposition of circulating immune complexes in small and medium sized blood vessels^[70]. These molecules are present in up to 50% of HCV-infected patients, although less than 15% have symptomatic disease^[71]. An independent association has been described between cryoglobulinaemia and steatosis, and advanced fibrosis^[72]. Clinical features of mixed cryoglobulinaemia include cutaneous vasculitis^[73], membranous proliferative glomerulonephritis^[74], and peripheral neuropathy^[75]. Treatment is aimed at the underlying virus. Other extrahepatic manifestations include:

- Ø Lympho-proliferative disorders such as lymphoma
- Ø Dermatological problems including porphyria cutanea tarda
- Ø Endocrine disorders such as thyroid dysfunction and diabetes mellitus Various rheumatological syndromes including Sjogren's syndrome and HCV related arthritis^[68]

DIAGNOSIS:

A combination of serological and molecular assays (nucleic acid amplification tests) is needed to diagnose HCV infection, guide treatment decisions, and assess response to antiviral treatment. Screening for antibodies against HCV and HCV-RNA testing are techniques used to establish diagnosis of previous or current infection. The HCV genotype determines treatment duration and drug dosage. Molecular assays are also used to define therapeutic response during and at the end of treatment and the sustained virological response (HCV-RNA not detected 6 months after end of

treatment)^[76]. Patients with suspected acute or chronic HCV infection should be assessed with both an anti-HCV enzyme immunoassay and a sensitive HCV-RNA assay. Acute infection is likely if HCV-RNA is detected without an HCV antibody response which is confirmed by seroconversion days to weeks later and may be delayed or even absent in HIV-infected individuals and other immune-compromised groups^[52]. In this setting, acute HCV infection is difficult to distinguish from an acute exacerbation of chronic HCV or from another cause of hepatitis in a patient with chronic HCV, unless an earlier serum sample for HCV testing is available. If neither antibody nor RNA are detectable, acute HCV infection is highly unlikely. The presence of both HCV antibody and RNA in a patient is generally suggestive of chronic HCV infection, particularly in people with signs of chronic liver disease, although these results are also consistent with the recent infection, which can spontaneously clear up^[76]. HCV antibody presence and absence of HCV-RNA concord with spontaneous viral clearance or successful treatment. To exclude the possibility of a false-positive antibody result in this situation, alternative serological assays should be used to verify antibody findings.

Anti-HCV drugs:

Before 1989, HCV wasn't identified and it was known as NANB hepatitis. As a trial, acyclovir was used to treat NANB, however it was useless [77]. Then, interferons (IFNs), which were efficiently used to treat hepatitis B, successfully treated NANB hepatitis. Interferons (IFNs) are signaling proteins, which are released normally in the body in response to different pathogens such as viral infection to interfere with the virus replication [78]. The US FDA approved IFN- α as the first anti-HCV drug at 1991, and after HCV identification. However, the use of IFNs alone led to relapse and low sustained virological response rate (SVR). Different studies were done to reach the suitable drug combinations, dose and duration of treatment to achieve high SVR. In this review, anti-HCV drugs have been categorized into three groups which discussed as follows:

PEGylated interferon/RBV:

After failure of IFNs therapy alone, FDA approved combination of IFN and RBV at 1998. This

combination achieved high SVR (high viral load) rates (34% after 6 months and 42% after 12 months of treatment)^[79]. With PEGylation of INF (addition of polyethylene glycol [PEG]) further enhanced virological response was achieved. PEGylated INF (PEG-INF) has a longer circulation time and a positive SVR rate combined with RBV was higher^[80-81]. Accordingly, in 2001, the FDA approved the combination of PEG-INF and PEG-INF / RBV and the 6-12 month scheme was considered the standard one until 2011^[82]. Despite success of this combination in eradicating the virus, some virus genotypes were not efficiently cured and dependently, led to emergence of new anti-HCV agents such as DAAs (direct acting antiviral agents)^[83,84].

Direct acting antivirals (DAAs):

DAAs act directly on the HCV itself, targeting certain steps in its life cycle. Depending on the mechanism of action and viral targets (enzymes or proteins), four classes were developed. Class 1 is NS3/4A protease inhibitors such as glecaprevir, paritaprevir, voxilaprevir and grazoprevir. This class acts via blocking viral protease enzyme, which is responsible for replication. Class 2 is nucleoside and nucleotide nonstructural protein 5B (NS5B) polymerase inhibitors (such as Sofosbuvir). These inhibitors attach to viral RNA, preventing it from replication. Class 3 is nonstructural protein 5A (NS5A) inhibitors. NS5A is a viral protein, which was blocked to prevent the virus from multiplying. Includes ledipasvir, daclatasvir, ombitasvir, pibrentasvir and elbasvir in this class. Last but not least, NS5B polymerase non-nucleoside inhibitors such as dasabuvir are incorporated into HCV which leads to the end of virus reproduction^[85]. DAAs should be combined together or with PEG-INF or RBV in order to enhance the antiviral effect and SVR rates. DAAs dramatically improved treatment of HCV in shorter times and with lower side effects. Therefore, the WHO recommends the wide use of DAAs to enable hepatitis C patients in all the countries from reaching this therapy and living better life. However, the existing limitations of DAAs such as difficult access to this expensive treatment, emergence of viral resistance due to its high mutation rate and risk of developing some adverse effects such as hepatocellular carcinoma, led to evolution of another line of HCV treatment, known as HTAs.

Host targeting antivirals:

HTAs emerged to address DAAs deficiencies. HTAs are considered, reviewed in, to be promising

therapy for HCV infections. HTAs act by interfering with the host enzymes and cellular factors required for the HCV life cycle or by improving the host immunity. It could be through host cell entry, replication, or assembly factors that interfere with the virus life cycle^[86]. Potent anti-HCV activity with anti-CD81, anti-SRBI monoclonal antibodies, EGFR inhibitor (erlotinib), or NPC1L1 inhibitor (ezetimibe) has been reported to prevent HCV entry^[86-89]. One replication inhibitor is microRNA (miRNA), which is non-coding RNA and is used for sequestration of miRNA-122. miRNA-122 is expressed in liver cells and it helps the virus RNA propagation. Additionally, antisense oligonucleotide (miravirsin) specifically targets and inhibits miR-122. Cyclophilin A (CypA) inhibitors (alisporivir/Debio 025, SCY-635 and NIM811) also disrupt the complex of CypA-NS5A, preventing HCV replication and enhancing the host immune response to virus inhibitors^[90]. Alpha-glucosidase inhibitors (such as MX-3253) interfere with HCV assembly via misfolding of the virus envelope glycoproteins^[91,92]. Due to acting on cellular targets, which is associated with very low mutations, HTAs have higher genetic barriers for resistance.

HCV Vaccination:

Global Health Sector Strategy on viral hepatitis (2016-2021) wishes to drastically decrease the new HCV infections by 90% in 2030, which in turn requires affordable access to effective prevention and treatment options all over the world. Despite the ongoing research on treatment of HCV-infected patients, there is still a big demand for vaccination against this virus to avoid the risk of disease transmission between individuals^[93,94]. This interprets why there is no available commercial vaccine against HCV, which was identified since 1989. Recent understanding of HCV structure and discovery of some conserved immune system stimulant parts of the virus (such as 5 and 3 UTR) resulted in inspiring possibilities of vaccination against HCV. Therefore, scientists keep seeking a promising vaccine to provide a hope in HCV-free world. Candidates for a promising and affordable HCV vaccine must be able to induce vigorous and prolonged humoral and cellular immune responses to the various genotypes of the virus and prevent the spread of virus among cells^[95]. Additionally, preventive vaccine should be able to induce production of nAbs to inhibit the virus from reaching target cells^[96]. HCV vaccination could be approached via prophylactic or therapeutic (as an adjunct to HCV antiviral therapy) vaccines. Classical vaccines, which are prepared from whole virus (inactivated or attenuated), are not

recommended with HCV due to biohazard concerns. However, attention has been focused on the use of new vaccination strategies including recombinant proteins (such as recombinant HCV E1 and E2 proteins, recombinant HCV core and NS3-NS4-NS5A-NS5B proteins)^[97-98], synthetic peptides^[99-100], dendritic cells, virosome-based vaccines and DNA-based vaccines [101] to produce a safe vaccine. These new vaccine approaches are still under clinical trials. Moreover, HCV vaccine could be designed to have multiple epitopes to induce a strong multi-immune response^[102-103].

Pharmaceutical Interventions for the Improvement of Anti-HCV Therapy:

Advances in drug delivery systems (DDS) significantly improved the pharmaceutical problems associated with the use of conventional DDS-related antiviral therapy. Advanced DDS involves the lipid polymers composed of particulate carriers. Advanced DDS improved the pharmacokinetic profile and stability of drugs, tissue damage to the sites affected by extravasation and drug targeting (Table 1); Advanced DDS consisting of liposomes and formulations based on lipids are designed to create a more stabilised PEG drug complex by linking PEG to interferons^[104]. Classical liposomes also known as 1st generation liposomes exhibit several limitations related to the variability in pharmacokinetics of anti-HCV drugs. Serum proteins affect the drug entrapment in classical liposomes. Incorporation of cholesterol resolved this problem in such a way that it entrapped the drug contents and reduced the leakage of drug. The rapid clearance of drugs from 1st generation liposomes was also problematic. Uptake of these liposomes by mononuclear phagocytes in the liver and spleen results in exacerbation of site specific toxicity and decrease in drug distribution to other tissues. Increasing the half-life of circulating liposomes resolved this issue as mononuclear phagocytes were blocked^[105]. Liposomal DDS release triggered allows anti-HCV drugs to reach target sites and improves therapeutic outcomes. There are two types of release triggers for liposomal DDS drugs^[106]. Heat, ultrasound and light may act as remote triggers for the release of liposomal DDS, whereas local triggers include enzymes and pH changes. Development of nanoparticles improves drug targeting, increases efficacy and prevents the adverse effects of anti-HCV drugs and the drugs used against HCV induced cancer. The liver, spleen and reticuloendothelial system takes on nanoparticles. Particulate matter with diameters of 100 nm or less is highly accessible to the target site. Nanoparticles with hydrophobicity are absorbed by the liver while those

with lipophilia are absorbed by the spleen and reticuloendothelial system^[107]. Drugs used against HCV-induced cancer are designed to increase permeability and retention at the target site, inhibit angiogenesis and target the vasculature of tumors [108]. Ribavirin, a nucleoside inhibitor used to treat hepatitis viral genome, is accompanied by accumulation of red blood cells (RBCs) that cause hemolytic anaemia^[109-110]. Scientists have therefore designed poly (glycerol-adipate) nanoparticles labelled with rhodamine B isothiocyanate (RBITC-PGA) to target ribavirin specifically to the liver and thereafter to decrease the RBC's take-up rate. These ribavirin nanoparticles could therefore improve HCV therapy by improving the targetability of drug delivery to hepatocytes and endocytic mechanisms^[111]. Hyaluronic acid (HA) in combination with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) has also been found to have a high serum biological activity and chemical stability compared to poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) nanoparticles^[112]. This HA-AuNP nano-complexes was therefore investigated as a delivery vehicle of interferon- α for HCV infection therapy. Seven days after injection of interferon- α encapsulated within HA-AuNP, it was observed that this complex was successfully and specifically delivered to the murine hepatic tissue, while PEG-interferon- α nanoparticles were not observed in the hepatocytes. Finally, it was concluded that the target-specific nano-complex HA-AuNP / interferon- α was effectively useful in the systemic management of HCV infection^[112]. On the other hand, hepatic transplantation, the currently available ESLD therapy mainly caused by HCV, has critical obstacles with regard to the shortage of transplantable liver tissue and the discharge of the graft^[113]. In one study PEG di-acrylate (PEG-DA)-based nanogel, a non-toxic material, was synthesized to create a platform of three dimensional artificial human liver tissues by entrapment of human progenitor cells in this platform that maintained the hepatic features [114]. This new nanogel platform has exciting consequences for tissue engineering and HCV therapy studies. FDA has approved two recombinant alpha interferons as initial therapy for chronic hepatitis C. It was recommended in 1991 that three million units (MU) of interferon alfa-2b could be given three times per week for a period of 6 months^[115]. In 1996, the use of 3 MU of interferon alpha-2a was also approved, three times a week for subcutaneous administration for a 12 month period. Other drugs examined for the treatment of HCV infection included interferon alpha-n1, consensus interferon, interferon derived from leukocytes and several beta interferons. The standardisation and assessment of the comparative biological potency of

Table 1: Pharmaceutical interventions for improving safety and efficacy of anti-HCV drugs.

Problems	Conventional drug delivery system	Advances drug delivery system	Example of intervention	Ref.
Degradation of interferon	Degradation by metabolism, shorter half life, rapid renal clearance, production of antibodies	Pegylation to prevent degradation, immunogenicity and increasing half life	Increase in the stability of Interferon alpha2a through pegylation	116, 117, 118
Poor stability	Reduced incorporation of hydrophobic drug in aqueous medium	Liposomes provide the hydrophilic and hydrophobic environment for incorporation of drugs	Increase in the stability of interferon with liposomes followed by pegylation	119
Tissue damages on extravasation of drugs	Inadvertent extravasations of toxic drugs causes tissue damages	Advanced DDS reduces the tissue damages by extravasation due to slow drug release	Formulation of ribavirin containing liposomes to prevent hemolysis	120
Poor biodistribution	The drug widely distributes so that it causes damage to unrelated tissues	In controlled release DDS, the drug releases slowly so that volume of drug distribution is lowered which reduces side effects	Biodegradable microspheres of interferons to increase the efficacy and dose related adverse effects	121
Rapid clearance	Rapid clearance of drugs through kidney necessitates administration of high dose or continuous infusion	In advanced DDS, the clearance of the drug is decreased altering the pharmacokinetics of drug	Pegylation, attachment of dextran or crosslinking of proteins decreases clearance of interferon	122
Lack of target tissue selectivity	The drug is widely distributed so that the concentration of drug is low at the target site resulting in reduced therapeutic effect	In advanced DDS, the concentration of the drug is high at the target site	Increased liver targeting of ribavirin with niosomes. Nanoparticle formulations of ribavirin can be used for viral infections in the brain. Surface of nano-carriers is modified so as to increase the delivery of ritonavir to cells	123, 124

different interferons remains problematic, however.

Conclusion & future perspective of nanomedicine-based HCV therapy:

Like any serious viral infections, HCV is a global issue of concern, which affects millions of people with negative effects on health and socioeconomic development. Since the discovery of HCV in 1989, there is an emergence of a huge number of new treatments, promising HCV patients a better life. With the ability to combine and integrate tools, nanotechnology offers a powerful contribution to the future of HCV prevention, diagnosis and treatment through imparting unique features to the drugs. These unique features include surface functionalization with one or more targeting ligands, imparting high specificity and affinity to liver cells and consequently off-target accumulation, which results in very low side

effects^[125]. On the other hand, the ability of nanosystems to house more than one therapeutic moiety could result in multivalent drug therapy with controlled release behavior. Additionally, HCV gene therapy, such as using siRNA, would not be successful without a nanocarrier, which is able to efficiently condensate and deliver intact genetic materials to their targets, affecting the virus life cycle. Nanomedicine, which is able to protect and control fate of the encapsulated drug, has enormous abilities to draw a clear future of HCV therapy through overcoming several challenges. Some of these challenges include viral resistance, patient access to effective treatment, shortening the duration of treatment and availability of prophylactic vaccines to prevent further spread of HCV. Emergence of HCV resistance remains for the moment as a major challenge to overcome. Due to its low genetic barrier to resistance^[126], which requires

the search for new treatment regimens, effective DAAs monotherapy could be hindered. Nanosystems, however, which have the ability to house more than one therapeutic moiety, could easily deliver different combination therapies for HCV, reducing the risk of failure in the treatment[127]. On the other hand, HTAs have a higher genetic barrier to resistance than DAAs, based on the mechanism of action. Many of these HTAs are genetic materials, which need promising nanocarriers to be efficiently delivered to their targets, overcoming DAA shortcomings. Parallel to development of effective anti-HCV therapy, global elimination of the virus depends also on reducing the cost of these treatment and improving the patient's access to these drugs. The proposed nanosystems are anticipated to reduce the encapsulated dose while keeping on sufficient drug efficacy [128]. Reducing the dose of expensive drugs will result in reduction of the total production cost and consequently, treatment will be extended to all HCV patients. The current 6-week therapy is of long duration, and shortening to four weeks or less appears to be a challenge to improve patient compliance[129]. Encapsulation of anti-HCV agents within surface-modified and functionalized nanosystems results in optimised dosing of the drug and increased delivery to the target site. Surface functionalization with certain targeting moieties has the ability to direct anti-HCV containing nanosystem toward liver cells, where the virus mainly multiplies. It is believed that with engineered nanosystems bearing moieties to target its delivery, there is a hope to shorten treatment duration for all HCV populations. Many HCV patients are unaware of their infection and are considered as a main reservoir for infection especially among young persons who inject drugs. Using nanotechnology, a prophylactic vaccine, which was not available till now and is considered a necessity to prevent further spread of the virus globally, could be approached.

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